

The two levels of the EUREKA subject model

Crop farming	Livestock	Forestry	Environment	Society	Economics
Biomass production	Biomass production	Biomass production	Biomass production	Biomass production	Biomass production
Agro-ecology	Aquaculture	Agro-ecology	Aquaculture	Agro-ecology	Aquaculture
Organic farming	Agro-ecology	Digitalisation	Agro-ecology	Organic farming	Agro-ecology
Digitalisation	Organic farming	Farm diversification/ new business models	Organic farming	Digitalisation	Organic farming
Farm diversification/new business models	Digitalisation	Competitiveness	Digitalisation	Farm diversification/ new business models	Digitalisation
Competitiveness	Farm diversification/new business models	AKIS	Farm diversification/ new business models	Competitiveness	Farm diversification/ new business models
Crop rotation/crop diversification	Competitiveness	Farming equipment and machinery	Competitiveness	AKIS	Competitiveness
AKIS	AKIS	Landscape/land management	Crop rotation/crop diversification	Animal husbandry and welfare	Crop rotation/crop diversification
Farming equipment and machinery	Farming equipment and machinery	Pest/disease control	AKIS	Plant production and horticulture	AKIS
Plant production and horticulture	Animal husbandry and welfare	Soil management/ functionality	Animal husbandry and welfare	Landscape/land management	Farming equipment and machinery
Pest/disease control	Plant production and horticulture	Genetic resource	Plant production and horticulture	Pest/disease control	Animal husbandry and welfare
Fertilisation and nutrients management	Pest disease/control	Energy management	Landscape/land management	Soil management/ functionality	Plant production and horticulture
Soil management/ functionality	Genetic resource	Farming/forestry competitiveness	Pest/disease control	Genetic resource	Landscape/land management
Genetic resource	Energy management	Biodiversity and nature management	Fertilisation and nutrients management	Energy management	Pest/disease control
Energy management	Supply chain, marketing & consumption	Waste, by-products & residues management	Soil management/ functionality	Supply chain, marketing & consumption	Fertilisation and nutrients management
Supply chain, marketing & consumption	Farming/forestry competitiveness	Climate and climate change, air	Genetic resource	Farming/forestry competitiveness	Soil management/ functionality
Farming/forestry competitiveness	Food quality processing & nutrition		Energy management	Food quality processing & nutrition	Genetic resource
Food quality processing & nutrition	Biodiversity and nature management		Supply chain, marketing & consumption	Biodiversity and nature management	Energy management
Biodiversity and nature management	Waste, by-products & residues management		Farming/forestry competitiveness	Waste, by-products & residues management	Supply chain, marketing & consumption
Waste, by-products & residues management	Climate and climate change, air		Food quality processing & nutrition	Climate and climate change, air	Farming/forestry competitiveness
Climate and climate change, air			Biodiversity and nature management		Food quality processing & nutrition
			Waste, by-products & residues management		Waste, by-products & residues management
			Climate and climate change, air		Climate and climate change, air

The two levels of the EUREKA subject model

Definitions of Level 1 subject categories

Crop farming

The cultivation of plants for food, animal feed, or other commercial uses.

Livestock

The activity of raising domesticated animals in an agricultural setting to produce labor and commodities such as meat, eggs, milk, fur, leather, and wool.¹

Forestry

Managing and using trees, forests and their associated resources for human benefit.

Environment

The natural environment encompasses all living and nonliving things occurring naturally, meaning in this case not artificial.²

Society

People in general thought of as living together in organized communities with shared laws, traditions, and values.³

Economics

Economics focuses on the actions of human beings, based on assumptions that humans act with rational behavior, seeking the most optimal level of benefit or utility. The building blocks of economics are the studies of labor and trade. Since there are many possible applications of human labor and many different ways to acquire resources, it is the task of economics to determine which methods yield the best results.⁴

Definitions of Level 2 subject categories

Biomass production

Production of the biodegradable fraction of products, waste and residues from biological origin - from agriculture (including vegetal and animal substances), forestry and aquaculture, as well as the biodegradable fraction of industrial and municipal waste⁵.

Aquaculture

Aquaculture is the farming of aquatic organisms, including fish, molluscs, crustaceans and aquatic plants⁶.

Agro-ecology

Agroecology is a holistic and integrated approach that simultaneously applies ecological and social concepts and principles to the design and management of sustainable agriculture and food systems⁷.

Organic farming

¹ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Livestock>

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Natural_environment

³ <https://www.merriam-webster.com/dictionary/society>

⁴ <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/e/economics.asp>

⁵ https://knowledge4policy.ec.europa.eu/bioeconomy/topic/biomass_en#agriculture

⁶ <https://www.fao.org/3/x6941e/x6941e04.htm>

⁷ <https://www.fao.org/agroecology/home/en/>

The two levels of the EUREKA subject model

Organic Agriculture is a production system that sustains the health of soils, ecosystems, and people. It relies on ecological processes, biodiversity and cycles adapted to local conditions, rather than the use of inputs with adverse effects⁸.

Digitalisation

Use of technology to convert precise data into actionable knowledge to drive and support complex decision-making on-farm and along the value chain⁹.

Farm diversification/new business models

Farm diversification refers to the trend towards gaining income from diverse activities (e.g. agri-tourism, processing of farm products)¹⁰.

Competitiveness

Competitiveness is the ability of the farm to compete and be successful.

Crop rotation/crop diversification

Crop rotation is growing a different crop on a given land area every growing/planting cycle and season¹¹. Crop diversification refers to the addition of new crops or cropping systems to agricultural production on a particular farm taking into account the different returns from value-added crops with complementary marketing opportunities¹².

AKIS

The term Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS) is used to describe the whole knowledge exchange system: the ways people and organisations interact within a country or a region. AKIS can include farming practice, businesses, authorities, research, etc. and can vary a lot, depending on the country or sector¹³.

Farming equipment and machinery

All machines and tools that are used in the production, harvesting, transport and storage of farm products.

Animal husbandry and welfare

The branch of agriculture concerned with the production, management, and breeding of animals.

Plant production and horticulture

Plant production refers to the cultivation of plants for food, feed, fiber, medicinal and cosmetic purposes. Horticulture is defined as that branch of agriculture concerned with growing plants that are used by people for food, for medicinal purposes, and for aesthetic gratification.

Landscape/land management

Land management concerns all operations, practices and treatments used to protect the land and enhance the goods and services provided by the ecosystem that the land is part of.

Pest/disease control

⁸ <https://www.ifoam.bio/why-organic/organic-landmarks/definition-organic>

⁹ Adapted from <https://www.dictionary.com/browse/digital-technology>

¹⁰ Adapted from https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Farm_typology

¹¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/crop-rotation>

¹² <https://www.ctc-n.org/technologies/crop-diversification-and-new-varieties>

¹³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/publications/eip-agri-brochure-agricultural-knowledge-and>

The two levels of the EUREKA subject model

Any measures, practices and strategies applied to prevent the appearance or spread of pests and diseases in plant production or to limit their impact on plant growth, crop yield and product quality.

Fertilisation and nutrients management

Careful management, monitoring and amending of soil fertility to meet crops' needs and to maintain environmental quality.

Soil management/functionality

Management of soil by focusing on differences in soil types and soil characteristics to define specific interventions that are aimed to enhance the soil health and quality for the selected land use.

Genetic resource

Any genetic material of plant and animal origin of actual or potential value for food and agriculture.

Energy management

All practices and measures applied for the efficient and responsible use of energy resources in agricultural production systems.

Supply chain, marketing and consumption

The full chain of activities and network among the actors for the preparation of a product or service starting from the raw material production till the marketing and consumption.

Farm/forestry competitiveness and diversification

Improvement of the competitiveness of the agriculture and forestry sectors, as well as the quality of life in rural areas and encouragement of diversification of economic activities.

Food quality/processing and nutrition

All aspects concerned with processing, preparing, preserving and distributing foods and beverages, their quality characteristics and nutritional value.

Biodiversity and nature management

Management and sustainable development of nature and conservation of diversity within species, between species and of ecosystems.

Waste, by-products and residues management

Managing waste in an environmentally sound manner and making use of the secondary materials they contain.

Climate and climate change

Climate is the average weather in a given area over a longer period of time. A description of a climate includes information on, e.g. the average temperature in different seasons, rainfall, and sunshine. Also a description of the (chance of) extremes is often included.¹⁴

Climate change is a long-term change in the average weather patterns that have come to define Earth's local, regional and global climates.

¹⁴ <https://www.climateurope.eu/what-is-climate-and-climate-change/>